

Name Convention

The Project **Urban PERISCOPE** INTEGRATED/0918/0034 is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus through the Research Innovation Foundation.

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Abstract

Within the UP project, the naming convention follows the requirements specified in BS1192: 2007 (Collaborative production of architectural, engineering and construction information – Code of practice) and will be used to name all kinds of FILES referring to the HBIM models, namely 3D BIM models, point clouds, mesh, models, CAD files, drawings, reports, simulation files, etc., that are stored in the Common Data Environment (CDE).

Even if somewhat more complex than other systems the choice of the BS1192 regulation is based on its widespread diffusion. The new ISO 19650-3 should provide an international standard for the naming convention in the foreseeable future.

The naming convention does not apply to a huge amount of data collected together, like geometric survey files (photographs, scan files), mesh models files, historical data, LCA files, or internal documents; in this case, the naming convention could apply to the folder in where the data are stored. The naming convention should generally be applied to the files directly produced within the project that are most important for the HBIM process (such as all the files linked to the HBIM models, simulation files, etc.). Nevertheless, a general name coding has been set for the internal needs of the UP project. The name will be composed of single fields of code, representing the file's metadata so that the name itself will provide information without the file being opened. Names should be created by joining together the codes in the specified fields, in the specified order, using the “-” hyphen character.

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MODEL NAMING CONVENTIONS

Names should be created by joining together codes in the specified field, in the specified order, using only the “_” hyphen character, which is therefore not allowed in any code. All letters will be in uppercase.

No spacing between elements should use.

The use of “.” and “-” are prohibited in the field code.

The “_” has to be used for the separation between fields.

Note: *If any description is optionally appended it shall be preceded by an underscore “_”. The hyphen character should not be used in a description field. The descriptive text should not be used to imply further distinction of meaning.*

1.1 General Model Naming Convention

- Field 1: **Project** (UP – Urban PeriScope)

An abbreviated code or number identifying the project.

- Field 2: **Historical area** (up to 4 characters)

Identifier of which historical area the model file relates to.

Limassol: LIM

Strovolos: STR

- Field 3: **Work Package and Project deliverable or milestone** (5 characters)

An abbreviated code identifying the originating Work package and the relative project deliverable or milestone.

- Field 3: **Partner** (Recommended 4 characters)

An abbreviated code identifying the originating stakeholder or Partner – see section 2.6.

- Field 4: **Discipline** (up to 4 characters)

Discipline identifier code – see section 2.1.

- Field 5: **Description** (optional)

Descriptive field to define the type of data portrayed in the file. Avoid repeating information codified in other fields. Can be used to describe any part of the previous fields, or to further clarify any other aspect of the contained data. In case the file is related to a cultural heritage building the UP team shall fill in this field the building code (e.g., “αριθμός τεμαχίου”).

- Field 6: **Type of document**

For example, Point cloud, Scan, Model, Drawing etc. – see section 2.4.

- Field 7: **Revision**

Descriptive field to define the revision of the file. Could be WIP01 in case of a “working in progress” model, and the first revision.

Kind reminder: Work in progress: WIP

Shared: SHR

Published: PUB

Archive: ARC

Example: Model File Name Description
UP_STR_7D.01_CYI_ARC_2.578_M3_WIP01

1.2 Level Naming Convention

Level names shall be done according to the General Specifications of the UP project.

This code indicates the level of the file within the project. The code can be letters or numbers and is two digits long. If the file refers to multiple levels (for example a BIM model or point cloud of the whole building) the code is ZZ-. If no level is applicable (for example, report files, or graphical diagrams mapping alteration and decay patterns on exposed surfaces of elevations), the code is XX-.

For all the other files (for example, BIM (Revit), CAD plan drawings) where levels are applicable, the designations are:

- GF Ground Floor
- For floor levels above the ground floor, the floor number should be used as follows:
01 Floor 1
02 Floor 2, etc.
- For the mezzanine the prefix "M" should be used as follows:
M1 Mezzanine above level 01
M2 Mezzanine above level 02, etc.
- For all levels below the ground floor the prefix "B" should be used:
B1 Basement 1 level below ground floor
B2 Basement 2 level below ground floor etc.

Example: Naming Level Convention

GF+0.50

1.3 Family Naming Convention

Library object naming provides a unified approach to the identification of objects across the dataset and associated tools.

Names should be composed using characters A to Z, a to z, 0 to 9, and the _ underscore character

The following characters should not be used in names:

• , . ! " £ \$ % ^ & * () { } [] + = < > ? | \ / @ ' ~ # - ` ' `

The name should use the _ underscore character as the delimiter and use CamelCase (no spaces, and capitalized words) to simplify phrases. No spaces or other punctuation should be used.

The naming should be as follows:

- Field 1: **Author / Partner** (Recommended 4 characters)

Family author or partner name. If the family is created by a manufacturer but modified according to needs, UP (or partner name) should be used as the author.

- Field 2: **Discipline** (up to 4 characters)

Discipline identifier code.

- Field 3: **Type**

A short description of the type of object. E.g. Column, Door, LightingFixture etc.

- Field 3: **Subtype/Description**

Used to convey additional specialization information not captured in attribute data. Can be the predefined subtype.

Example: Family Naming Convention

CYI_ARC_Door_DoubleDoorWithDecoration_330

This convention applies to the family name of loadable families and the type of system families.

If a family contains different types, the type name must clearly define its specificity (either the specific dimensions or specific materials).

1.4 Material Naming Convention

The UP team must follow a standard material list and naming when they produce their 3D model.

Example: Material Naming Convention

CYI_ARC_Plaster_Blue

Each element in the 3D model must have a material assigned following the naming procedure detailed above.

1.5 Views Naming Convention

To automatize the Design Review and 3D Coordination, the views of the 3D model sent by the UP Designers need to be organized in the same way.

The value of a view parameter 'GEN_Classification' will be one of the following:

- **“WIP”** (Work In Progress) for the views which are used by the UP Designers for their work.
- **“Shared”** for the views which will be used by all the disciplines for coordination.
- **“Published”** for the views on sheets and published officially.

1.6 Planview Naming Convention

- Field 1: **Location** (up to 4 characters)

Identifier of which historical area the model file is located.

Limassol: LIM

Strovolos: STR

- Field 2: **Building Code** (up to 5 characters)

Identifier of which cultural heritage building the plan view relates to. (αριθμός τεμαχίου)

- Field 3: **Level**

- Field 4: **Description**

Example: Planview Name Convention

STR_2.578_GF+0.50_Ground Level

1.7 Section / Elevation Naming Convention

Note:

The default *Section 1* view will be considered temporary and should be deleted when purging the HBIM model.

Example: Section/ Elevation Name Convention

STR_2.578_Section_A-A

STR_2.578_Elevation_North

1.8 3D View Naming Convention

Example: 3D View Name Convention
STR_2.578_3D_InteriorView

1.9 Workset Naming Convention

Example: 3D View Name Convention
ARC_Interior

1.10 Views Titles Naming Convention on Sheets

The “sheet number” shall be the codification of the 2D deliverable and the “sheet name” description.

Example: Views Titles Naming Convention on Sheets
LIM_2.578_Section_A-A_1.100

1.11 Parameter Naming Convention

Parameter naming must not include spaces or hyphens.

1.11.1 Naming Convention for Shared Parameters

- Shared Parameter file

The shared parameter .txt file shall be named “SharedParameters_*ModelName*” and shall remain in the same folder as the model.

- Group of Shared Parameters

Discipline_Description

- The naming of Shared Parameters

Description

- Share the Parameter folder

Discipline_Shared Parameters

No shared parameters shall be created without discussion with the UP BIM manager.

1.11.2. Project Parameters

The following project properties need to be filled for every WIP file.

- Organization Name (Partner or stakeholder)
- Building Name (Building Code)
- Project Name
- Client Name (Municipality of Strovolos or Limassol)
- Name of the model

1.12 Naming for Drawings Publication

Example: Naming for drawing Publication

UP_CYI_ARC_STR_2.578_Section A-A_SHR01.pdf

1.13 Notes

1.13.1 Classification

The code refers to a description of the file using a standard classification, for example, Omniclass. The code is optional and will not be used.

1.13.2 Number

The sequential number is used when a container is one of a series, not distinguished by any other of the fields. The numbering is four integer numeric digits, used sequentially. When the file is unique or the first of the series, the Number is 0001-.

1.13.3.Suitability

The code refers to the approved “suitability” for use of the file, or the file status, that can be Work in Progress, Shared or Published. Following the ISO 19650-1, within the Common Data Environment, there will be folders with specific accesses to identify file status (e.g. Work in Progress, Shared, Published). Therefore the optional code will not be used.

1.13.4 Revision

The code refers to the revision phase. The code is optional and will not be used.

1.13.5 Description

Description of the file content. It is used only when the code for the file is not univocal and does not permit to identify it immediately. The description should be as brief as possible (no more than 8 digits) using CamelCase (no spaces, and capitalized words) to simplify phrases. No spaces or other punctuation should be used.

FIELDS CODES

2.1 Discipline Codification

Code	Discipline
ARC	Architectural
STR	Structural
MEP	Mechanical
SALE	Electrical
GSUR	Geometric Survey
NDT	Terrestrial non-destructive testing
LCI	Life-Cycle Inventory
LCA	Life-Cycle Impact Assessment
BI	BIM Implementation
VR	Virtual Reality

2.2 Historical Area Codification

Code	Historical Area
STR	Strovolos
LIM	Limassol

2.3. Floor Level Codification

Code	Floor Level
BS	Basement
LG	Lower Ground
GR	Ground Floor
MZ	Mezzanine
01	First Floor
02	Second Floor
ZZ	Multiple Floors
XX	No level applicable
UP	Upper Part of Building
LO	Lower Part of Building

2.4 Type Content Codification

Code	Type Content
DW	Drawings
SP	Specifications
SC	Schedules
DC	Documents
SK	Sketches
PT	Presentations
RD	Renderings
PR	Project Reports
CR	Cost Report
M3	Three Dimensional Model
CL	Content Library Model

CA	Ghost model (CAD files)
GR	Grids and Level Model
PTI	Point Clouds – Interior
PTE	Point Clouds – Exterior
MM	Mesh Model

2.5 File Type Codification

Code	File Type
DWG	Autocad File Format
DWF/ DWFx	Autodesk Design Review File
PDF	PDF File Format
RVT	Revit File Format
RTE	Revit Template Project File
E57	Point Cloud File
RCP	Recap File
OBJ	Mesh model File

2.6 Project Partner Codification

Code	Partner
CYI	The Cyprus Institute
CUT	The Cyprus University of Technology
FRC	Frederic Research Center
FBK	Fondazione Bruno Kessler
MI	Ministry of Interior – Town Planning and Housing Department
MS	The Municipality of Strovolos
LM	The Municipality of Limassol
HIT	HIT Hypertech Innovations Ltd
NetU	NetU Consultants Ltd
TALOS	RTD Talos Ltd

GENERAL FILE NAMING CONVENTION AND TEMPLATE

All the partners and stakeholders of the UP project must adopt the following name convention and document template for the documents that they produce.

- Field 1: **Project** (UP – Urban PeriScope)
An abbreviated code or number identifying the project.
- Field 2: **Work Package** (3 characters)
An abbreviated code identifying the originating Work package and the relative project deliverable or milestone.
- Field 3: **Project deliverable or milestone** (3 characters)
An abbreviated code identifying the relative project deliverable or milestone.
- Field 4: **Revision** (up to 3 characters)
- Field 5: **Description**
Descriptive field to define the type of data portrayed in the document. Avoid repeating information codified in other fields. Can be used to describe any part of the previous fields, or to further clarify any other aspect of the contained data.
- Field 6: **Editor** (Recommended up the 3 characters of the editor’s name and surname)
- Field 7: **Date** (6 characters)

Example: Model File Name Description

UP_WP7_D7.1_002_BIMImplementation_MDe_250320

Document template: <http://oc.cytera.cyi.ac.cy/index.php/s/2zCNYNkHPpLxW26>